

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DOMESTIC VIOLENCE IN A SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTEXT

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Abstract

The family is the main institution that plays a leading role in the socialization and psychological development of a person in society. It creates a basic environment for the formation of an individual as a personality, ensuring emotional stability and adaptation in social relations. However, cases of domestic violence are observed in some families, which negatively affects the psychological and physical health of family members, as well as harms the quality of family relations and the social well-being of society. Domestic violence manifests itself in various forms - physical, emotional, psychological and sometimes economic, and social, cultural and individual factors play a joint role in its occurrence. This problem is assessed as an important socio-psychological challenge not only at the individual level, but also at the societal level.

The article will analyze the socio-psychological aspects of domestic violence in the family, its causes, consequences and impact on individuals, especially children. Also, ways to prevent violence and strengthen the psychological protection of family members will be presented from a scientific perspective. This approach can contribute to strengthening the family institution and ensuring a healthy family environment.

Keywords: domestic violence, psychological trauma, women's rights, patriarchal norms, post-traumatic stress, social support.

Main text of the article. Violence is a means of control and suffering that consists of applying psychological, social, economic pressure or inflicting physical blows on a person. Violence begins psychologically. It is psychological violence that causes the greatest trauma to a person and leaves a long-term impact and mark. As a continuation of psychological violence, physical, sexual, and economic violence appear. This is a chain process. The person subjected to violence suffers more and more. It is important to take timely measures to prevent the chain process.

"The concept of violence can be viewed in a broad or narrow sense, but in each case its connection with the human personality can be seen. In a broad sense, violence is understood as a way of acting or coercion that harms others, restricts free choice, and prevents free will. In a narrow sense, the concept of violence is the infliction of physical, mental, material, or moral harm to a specific person or social group" [5, p.8].

There are different types of sickle cell disease. They are as follows:

- **Physical violence** - means causing physical harm to the other party. This mainly includes hitting, beating, slapping, and kicking, which can lead to various injuries to the body.
- **Emotional abuse** - refers to the collapse of the other party's inner world and spiritual harm.
- **Psychological violence** - can cause mental disorders and even death.
- **Economic violence** - it is intended to cause damage to the economic and material capabilities of the other party.
- **Sexual violence** - to provoke the other party into sexual intercourse without their consent.

"The forms of domestic violence defined by law are as follows:

- **Physical violence in the home** - intentional physical pressure by one person on another, that is, violating their safety by using force, beating them, harming their health, torturing them, or restricting their right to freedom;

- **Domestic psychological violence** - intentional psychological pressure exerted by one person on another or actions aimed at creating unbearable psychological conditions;

- **Application of illegal restrictions of an economic nature in the household** - one person deprives another of property or income in his possession, disposal or use, creates economic dependence, maintains such dependence or abuses it - actions aimed at using it;

- **Domestic sexual violence** - "one of these persons forces the other to perform sexual acts against his or her will" [3, p.13].

Since these forms of violence occur within the family and between people in close relationships, most of the time such acts are not perceived as violence.

Domestic violence has the following symptoms:

- ✓ if physical violence has occurred, it will be repeated and the severity of the violence will gradually increase;
- ✓ after the violence, the perpetrator declares that he will change and that these situations will not happen again;
- ✓ when the victim announces that they will cut off contact, the perpetrator threatens them;
- ✓ domestic violence occurs in any segment of the population, regardless of nationality, social, financial status, or other circumstances.

Domestic violence has "specific symptoms" that are common to all population groups:

- ✓ if there is one type of violence in a relationship, then it is highly likely that other forms of violence will also develop;

- ✓ all forms of domestic violence include elements of control and power by the perpetrator;
- ✓ the psychological and socio-cultural factors that lead to the perpetration of violence and the maintenance of a cycle of violence are often the same for different forms of domestic violence;
- ✓ the psychological trauma caused by violence and the symptoms experienced by victims of violence are the same for different forms of domestic violence.

Domestic violence not only undermines the foundations of the family, but also destroys the security foundations of society as a whole.

The main reason for this violence is the lack of awareness and neglect of human rights in society. There are also many laws against violence and the violation of women's rights. In 1979, the UN adopted the Convention on the elimination of violence against women and the elimination of all forms of discrimination against women. In 1981, 21 countries joined this Convention. To date, 181 countries have joined this Convention. In 1995? Azerbaijan ratified this convention. This convention consists of 30 articles, 10 of which relate to women's rights.

Violence is prevalent in almost all countries of the world. Many studies have shown that one in three women has been subjected to violence at some point, and at least one woman is killed every three minutes. 1 in 5 women in the worldwide a victim of sexual violence or attempted sexual assault in their lifetime. Every year, 3-4 million women are beaten by their partners. 95% of victims domestic violence are women and 80% of incidents are committed by men.

A phenomenal issue that has recently hindered the normal development of society - is domestic violence. What is domestic violence, what social problems does it cause and who is most exposed to this violence? In general, the term violence is understood as the application of various forms of coercion in relation to others. When we say "domestic violence", we mean domestic violence as an international term. That is, it is the desire of one family member to keep another family member under his control. This is especially noticeable in regions where patriarchal customs and traditions remain and prevail.

Domestic violence or family violence is commonly referred to as wife beating, violence against women, family member beatings, and marital strife. However, there are legal and clinical definitions of domestic violence. The legal definition of domestic violence is set out in the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the Prevention of Domestic Violence. On June 22, 2010, the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On the Prevention of Domestic Violence" was adopted. According to Article 1.0.1 of this law, domestic violence is "intentional physical or moral harm caused by one of the persons covered by this law to another by abusing close family relationships, joint or former joint residence". As for the clinical definition, domestic violence is "a sequence of humiliating and violent behaviors committed by adolescents, young people and adults against their intimate partners, such as physical violence, sexual violence, psychological pressure, economic dependence or deprivation".

"A victim of domestic violence is a person who has suffered physical or moral harm as a result of intentional acts (physical, mental, sexual and economic violence) committed against him or her by a family member, close relative, person not in a legal marriage or person with whom he or she previously lived together and is a "victim" of violence" [4, p.113-114].

Domestic violence or the choice to commit violence is more of a behavioral problem, and this problem usually becomes a learned process later, as a result of the extent to which the individual witnessed their parents committing violence against each other during their childhood. Patriarchal values and the choice to use violence to gain power and control are also one of the main reasons for the emergence of domestic violence.

Domestic violence is neither an argument nor a conflict. Argument and conflict are situations where parties disagree on certain issues and insist on their own position. In the process of domestic violence, there is no opportunity for equality between the parties. The perpetrator of violence uses physical force, economic opportunities and social status to control the victim.

Domestic violence or domestic violence-means forcing or using force to force the other party or parties to behave according to one's wishes and interests. When we think of violence, most of us think of physical violence such as "beating", "sexual rape", etc. But violence is not limited to these.

"Domestic violence, unlike other types of violence, is systematic in nature and does not become a random episode in the life of the person subjected to violence.

The second fundamental difference that distinguishes domestic violence from other types of violence is the relationship between the subject and object of violent acts. Thus, domestic violence does not occur randomly, between people who do not know each other, but between people who are in a close relationship with each other" [2, p.9]. From a behavioral perspective, violence or abuse can also occur between two people who do not know each other: for example, bullying, injury, murder, rape, kidnapping, enslavement, damage to property, intimidation. However, unlike others, people who experience domestic violence do not face these types of violence once, but continuously, and the effect of violence is exacerbated by the intimate nature of the relationship. In domestic violence, the perpetrator has constant access to the victim, knows the victim's daily lifestyle, and continuously inflicts physical violence on the victim, and is able to control and manage her daily life. The intimate or partner relationship of the abuser with the victim, as well as the fact that he lives in the same house with him, gives him this opportunity, and therefore, in domestic violence, the victim has very little chance of leaving the abuser and saving her life.

The problem of violence against women also touches on health issues, which are part of human rights. In most cases, the main cause of deaths, disabilities, and health problems among women of reproductive age is the result of domestic violence. At least one in five women in the world has been subjected to physical or sexual violence by men at some point. People with physical disabilities are more likely to experience

violence in the family. Since they belong to a more vulnerable group in society, violent attitudes towards them in the family should be the focus of attention. Usually, such people remain dependent on family members, caregivers, for their daily behavior patterns. A high level of dependence can be a basis for violence.

The one who advised to keep quiet about the incident is showing a very wrong path. In fact, the fact that people who have been injured repeatedly tell their story reduces the impact of the injury. This helps the person who has been subjected to violence to restore their mental balance even faster.

When we look at the scale of domestic violence and the dangers it poses, we find that even when the violence is directed against only one member of the family, other family members are also affected by its impact. This situation is called by experts the "second wave" or "repeat victimization." During interviews with witnesses of "repeat victims", it is revealed that they experience no less psychological stress than family members who have experienced violence. The victims of the "second wave" are mainly children who have witnessed violence. Such children are exposed to high risk and experience various emotional stresses.

A child who witnesses domestic violence is at risk of developing emotional and behavioral problems such as anxiety, depression, poor school performance, low self-esteem, nightmares, and physical illnesses. It has been shown that a number of consequences have been noted, including increased anxiety, mental and physical developmental delay, decreased intellectual abilities, isolation, increased distrust or fear of strangers, and difficulties in communicating with others. A tendency to aggressive behavior develops in childhood and adolescence, and the risk of a family model based on domestic violence increases when reaching adulthood.

No matter what form of violence she experiences, this violence that a woman experiences causes her to experience mental, psychological, sexual, and physical health problems. An unhealthy woman cannot raise healthy offspring, and at the same time, a child who witnesses or experiences violence during childhood will continue to experience this violence in every aspect of her life with feelings of hopelessness, depression, guilt, and ambivalence.

The man uses various excuses to psychologically abuse the woman at home, sets his own rules, and deprives the woman of all her rights. The social features of such a family dictator are assessed as follows:

- ✓ first of all, the concept of fairness is low;
- ✓ second, such men have low self-esteem;
- ✓ third, he strives for power by all violent means.

Although these types of men are usually intellectually weak, they have very strong complexes. The man who commits violence is not-consciously fears that the other party may be stronger and will reveal his weakness. The violent person aims to increase his dominance and control over the victim and achieve his own interests through this behavior. The man who insists on keeping the violence he has committed secret does not want his act to be discovered and the woman to be protected by others. It is believed that women who "want

to be beaten and deserve it" are beaten. That is why they do not leave their homes and endure all situations.

Women who are subjected to violence can leave their abuser at any time. In fact, psychological factors (specific psychological changes, taking a "victim position", not knowing their rights), as well as economic conditions (financial opportunities, lack of opportunity to live separately) prevent a woman from leaving her home.

Domestic violence is a very broad topic, it is both a man's violence against a woman and children, but also a woman's violence against a man and children, as well as pressure on the elderly in the family, which is also called domestic violence. Today, we have women who are beaten by their husbands, and men who are subjected to pressure, moral pressure, and sometimes physical violence by their wives.

Domestic violence is a learned behavior through observation and reasoning, both within the family and in society. This is not due to genetics or illness. Domestic violence is repeated because it is learned through experience. Domestic violence allows the perpetrator to exert control over their victim through intimidation.

One of the effective means of keeping a woman in a state of dependence is the threat of having her children taken away from her after a divorce and of them turning against her. Using this psychological influence, a man even creates the conditions for her to openly declare her infidelity to her wife.

Women are the most vulnerable targets of domestic violence, they are beaten, verbally abused, financially exploited, insulted, raped, injured and even killed. There are many reasons why a woman endures domestic violence: she feels powerless, she is financially dependent, she is afraid of social condemnation. Interestingly, in some cases, a woman even considers it normal.

"Most women prefer to forgive the first violence and abuse directed at them by their husbands in the family, thinking that this is the last resort and that the husband will not allow such a thing to happen again. When there are children in the family, the situation becomes even more complicated. Most women who have a liberal attitude towards the fact of violence get used to it, coming to terms with their fate ("A man beats and curses a man"). Low self-esteem and coming to terms with the impossibility of getting out of the situation are characteristic of such women. It is clear that the way out of conflicts and problems arising in the family cannot be violent means at all. The civilized way out of an inescapable, crisis-ridden situation may not be living together with a cruel partner, but divorce. A man who regularly raises his hand to a woman is, in fact, a person who has lost love for his wife, will never be able to improve himself, and his re-education is impossible" [1, p.321-322].

In general, it can be concluded that both men and women view domestic violence as a tradition and do not attempt to change it.

People who experience domestic violence experience symptoms of fear, insomnia, nightmares, self-blame, depression, loss of self-confidence, complex feelings, nervous breakdowns, loneliness, and irritability.

People living in a violent environment and those who have been victims of violence may experience a variety of feelings: terror, panic, helplessness, hopelessness or powerlessness, concerns about safety, feelings of guilt, discouragement, terrible nightmares, loss of self-confidence, unpleasant memories, feelings of anxiety, depression, phobias, sadness, suicidal tendencies, self-blame, loss of confidence, emotional turmoil, decreased sexual activity, alcohol and drug addiction, feelings of revenge, etc.

The consequences of domestic violence are often consistent with the symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder psychotherapy. The result of emotional distress can take various forms, such as a person's heightened sense of isolation and loneliness at home.

It is usually not considered acceptable to help someone who has experienced domestic violence seek counseling for family relationships. Because these people have developed a feeling that someone could reveal their family secrets, especially since the aggressors do not allow such meetings or advice to be given. It takes a certain amount of courage for a victim of violence to seek professional psychological help. In most cases, it takes years from the moment the violence occurred to seeking help.

Women who have been subjected to violence are not helpless or weak. They are not stupid. On the contrary, some are very confident. According to stereotypes formed in all societies, women who have been subjected to violence are portrayed as very weak, pitiful and crazy. They are not like that. Such women were not weak and crazy, but strong and resilient women. Of course, mistreatment can affect anyone.

It is necessary to take action against violence, to organize public condemnation of this act. There is a great need for people to be there for victims and support them. With this in mind, the creation of woman-to-woman support groups is very important. It is essential to have people who will stand by the victim and resist with them.

Social support is the best tool to reduce the psychological trauma experienced as a result of the incident. Thus, social support is a powerful motivating factor that can reduce the impact of the "helplessness and helplessness" syndrome. The presence of a woman who has been injured in a supportive and accepting social support environment is the best tool to help her recover from the post-traumatic stress disorder more quickly. Especially, the ability to discuss the events (pain and fear) together among a group of people who have experienced the same situation. It can reduce the impact of damage quite quickly.

The widespread prevalence of domestic violence is due to the concentration of power and authority in the hands of men in society, patriarchal ideas, toxic masculine behaviors, and religious beliefs such as the subordination of men to women being considered social norms. Violence against women is historically a manifestation of unequal power relations between women and men, which has led to men's dominance over women and discrimination against women, as well as the prevention of women's comprehensive development. The prevalence of domestic violence in society is caused by the direct or indirect participation of society

in this matter. Domestic violence is committed by relatives, acquaintances, people living in the same neighborhood, and neighbors outside the family. It becomes an even more socially charged scourge with the fact that its representatives justify the violence committed, always blame the victim, and traditionally believe that men should be dominant and control their partners.

Some beliefs of certain institutions also play an important role in the persistence of domestic violence. Among them, religion, media, education, legal and social assistance systems influence the continuation of violence: for example, religion emphasizes the importance of a woman's submission to her husband and the fact that a woman is her husband's property; the media's treatment of domestic violence cases as ordinary news and under-reporting; the failure to properly handle complaints from victims of violence; the lack of serious treatment and shaming of women who complain in police departments; the failure to give appropriate punishments to the perpetrator or the lack of monitoring of the implementation of the punishments given; backwardness in education, failure to instill in students from an early age that women and men are equal, truancy; the absence of a social work and social assistance system; doctors not suspecting that the injuries of a patient with any injury were caused by domestic violence or the lack of mechanisms to take appropriate steps even if it is known are among the factors that create conditions for domestic violence to spread in society. The normalization of the use of violence and the justification of the actions of the violent person by society leads to the widespread spread of domestic violence. The support of such beliefs by the police and other individuals in law enforcement agencies leads to the improper work of those who have a key role in solving and stopping domestic violence and the improper implementation of the law.

Domestic violence in Azerbaijan is still not considered a socially significant and state-important problem. As in other countries with strong patriarchal norms, society in Azerbaijan still considers men to be the owners and breadwinners of the home, so it is considered normal for them to punish and commit violence against their partners. The majority of people justify men's actions by citing phrases such as "A man can beat or love", "He is his own wife and he knows better", "What right does a wife have to make a man's word two?"

Due to the lack of relationships, as well as psycho-traumatic childhood experiences and parental behavior patterns, victimized women develop dependent personality traits, and use their own power to gain acceptance into the family system. They tend to sacrifice their "I". Psychological characteristics of female victim behavior in cases of domestic violence include: value distortion, neuroticism, a state of learned helplessness, lack of self-confidence and a deformed self-perception, affective dysfunction, inconsistency and conflict, violation of the boundaries of the "Ego". Female victims experience clinical consequences of domestic violence, and these symptoms are consistent with the symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder.

Violence is considered so normal that it is almost a common practice for both men and women to punish

women with violence for almost every small or big problem is considered normal by half of them. In particular, in Azerbaijan, women are also subjected to violence at home by their mothers, fathers and brothers before they get married. After marriage, this violence is replaced by violence from husbands, mothers-in-law and other first-degree relatives arising from marital relations. A mother who experiences violence is also prone to committing violence against her children, and a mother who is unable to express the aggression, hatred and resentment resulting from violence against the violent person sometimes directs this aggression against her children. Although in most cases, physical and psychological violence prevents a mother from devoting time and showing love to her children, when faced with violence by her violent husband, actively protecting and nurturing her child from that violence becomes a priority for that mother.

In Azerbaijani society, concepts such as religion, customs and traditional gender roles (that is, women should do housework and men should work and bring income to the home) instill stereotypical beliefs in people that men are the owners of the house, the wife in the house, and the children are the property of the man. This sense of ownership and ownership manifests itself in all aspects of a woman's life. A woman cannot make independent decisions about her clothing, where she goes, where she works, and even the choice of kindergarten and school for her children. This is especially true if a woman prefers "revealing" clothing and does not spend most of her day sitting at home, certain suspicions begin to arise about such women among the society around the family and among relatives who know them. If the woman's husband feels these doubts or directly opposes them, then an emotionally charged feeling emerges - a sense of honor and its inviolability. The causes of domestic violence in Azerbaijan include the woman's sexual infidelity and alleged betrayal, as well as the suspicion and anxiety observed in this regard by the violent husband. Stereotypical social norms, the family and environment in which the person grew up, and the state of mental health play a major role here. However, the concepts created by patriarchal social norms play a very large role here.

In societies where patriarchal values are strong, a man's honor depends on the actions of the woman in the family. A woman's honor is explained by her shyness, shyness, and lack of close relationships with men. In such societies, even the possibility of a woman meeting someone other than her husband is considered a stain on her husband's honor and dignity, a humiliation of his respect in society. If a man, who is aware of the possibility that his wife is meeting with another man, does not punish his wife with certain violent measures, that man is looked down upon in society and is called "not

a man". Therefore, the response to sexual infidelity often results in violence or honor killings.

One nuance that should be especially noted here is that betrayal and similar situations have a double standard and are a gender issue. So, if a man commits betrayal, society views it as normal and there is no need to even resort to bloodshed for it. However, if a woman commits betrayal, her act results in the most severe physical punishments, humiliating actions, and even death.

Since cases of bloodshed, anger, and self-absorption are often observed in families where domestic violence occurs regularly, members of these families are not inclined to take initiatives to improve the general welfare of the society and to act as socially active citizens. On the other hand, in families where domestic violence occurs, family members avoid close contact with the surrounding society in order to avoid any condemnation. This often happens because the violent member of the family isolates the family members from the environment socially and emotionally. Such low participation in society leads to indifference and lack of initiative towards cases of domestic violence and their adequate investigation.

According to psychologists, each specific fact of violence should be analyzed separately. Violence is undoubtedly an unpleasant offense, and both partners are guilty of its occurrence. A violent relationship model can never be considered the norm for a family.

Thus, domestic violence is a social problem that arises as a means of domination and control between intimate partners. Its negative effects not only harm individuals - the physical and mental health of women, the education and upbringing of children - but also seriously harm the social development of society. These problems are observed to be more widespread in environments where patriarchal values prevail. Preventing domestic violence, supporting victims and holding perpetrators accountable require the active participation of the state. As a society, we must oppose social stereotypes that normalize male dominance and take measures to reduce violence.

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